

MODELING OF MECHANICAL RESPONSE IN CFRP ANGLE-PLY LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

It is known that the failure process in angle-ply laminate involves matrix cracking and delamination and that they exhibit nonlinear stress-strain relation. There may be a significant effect of the constituent blocked ply thickness on the mechanical behavior of angle-ply laminates. These days, thin prepregs whose thickness is, for example 50 micron, are developed and commercially available. Therefore, we can design wide variety of laminates with various constituent ply thicknesses. In this study, effects of constituent ply thickness on the nonlinear mechanical behavior and the damage behavior of CFRP angle-ply laminates are investigated experimentally. Based on the experimental results, the mechanical response in CFRP angle-ply laminates is modeled by using the finite strain viscoplasticity model.

2 Experiment

Carbon/epoxy laminates with stacking sequences of $[(+45)_m/(-45)_n]_s$ (where $(m, n)=(4, 1), (2, 2)$ and $(1, 4)$) (laminates with 16 0.15mm-thick prepregs (conventional prepreg)) and $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$, (a laminate with 48 0.05mm-thick prepregs (thin-ply prepreg)) are used as specimens. It should be noted that the laminate thickness is almost the same (about 2.4mm), but the constituent (blocked) 45° or -45° ply thicknesses are quite different. This situation is shown in Fig.1 schematically. In the 16 0.15mm-thick prepreg laminates (Fig.1(a)-(c)), the constituent ply thickness ranges from 0.6mm to 0.15mm regarding the blocked plies as a continuous constituent ply. In the 48 0.05mm-thick prepreg laminate (Fig.1(d)), the constituent ply thickness is 0.05mm. Monotonic tensile tests at different strain rates, loading-unloading test and stress-relaxation tests are conducted.

Figure 1. Schematics of laminate configurations used in this study (t : thickness of constituent (blocked) ply). (a) $[(+45)_4/(-45)_4]_s$, (b) $[(+45)_2/(-45)_2]_s$, (c) $[(+45)/(-45)]_s$ and (d) $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$

3 Results and discussion

Figure 2 shows the stress-strain curves obtained by the monotonic tensile test. It was found that the laminate strength and the ultimate strain are higher for the laminates with thinner constituent plies. There is little effect of constituent ply thickness on mechanical response within small strain regime. It also seems that laminates with relatively thin constituent plies exhibit apparent nonlinear mechanical response. They exhibit *softening-hardening behavior*, which may be due to the fiber angle rotation.

Therefore, we made an attempt to estimate the fiber angle change and resulting current laminate Young's modulus. We estimated the current fiber angle θ by using the strain data and the following equation.

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{1 + \varepsilon_x}{1 + \varepsilon_y} \quad (1)$$

where ε_x and ε_y are longitudinal and transverse strains, respectively. We estimated current laminate Young's modulus by using the classical lamination

theory. Figure 3 shows the estimated ply angle and Young's modulus changes of CFRP (+45/-45) angle-ply laminates as a function of (a) longitudinal strain and (b) stress (strain rate= 9.3×10^{-5}). We found that as the longitudinal strain increases the fiber angle decreases and the resulting Young's modulus increases extensively. So we confirm that we have to consider the effect of fiber angle rotation when modeling the mechanical behavior of these laminates.

Figure 2. Stress-strain curves of laminates with different constituent ply thicknesses.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Estimated ply angle and Young's modulus changes of CFRP (+45/-45) angle-ply laminates as a function of (a) longitudinal strain and (b) stress (strain rate= 9.3×10^{-5})

Figure 4 shows the effect of strain rate on the stress-strain relation for the laminate with different constituent ply thicknesses. It can be seen that as the strain rate increases the stress increases. The stress relaxation behavior and loading-unloading curves are also shown. Considering that we see both the strain rate effect and stress-relaxation behavior, we need a viscoplasticity model to describe the material mechanical behavior.

(a) 0.6mm

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(b) 0.3mm

(d) 0.05mm

(c) 0.15mm

Figure 4. Stress-strain curves of (+45/-45) angle-ply CFRP laminates with different ply thicknesses at various strain rates. Stress relaxation and loading-unloading curves are also shown. Constituent ply thicknesses are (a) 0.6mm, (b) 0.3mm, (c) 0.15mm and (d) 0.05mm.

Figure 5 shows the appearance of the fractured laminates, which indicates that extensive matrix cracks and delaminations occur in the laminates with thinner constituent plies. We also observe necking in the transverse direction and swelling phenomena in the thickness direction. Figure 6 shows damage progress in CFRP angle-ply laminates (constituent ply thickness $t=0.05\text{mm}$, strain rate= $9.3 \times 10^{-5}/\text{s}$) observed by the edge replica technique. Based on this observation, we evaluated the matrix crack density as a function of loading. Figure 7 shows the crack density in CFRP angle-ply laminates with various constituent ply thicknesses as a function of applied strain (strain rate= $9.3 \times 10^{-5}/\text{s}$).

Figure 5. Appearance of fractured specimens.

Figure 6. Damage progress in CFRP angle-ply laminates (constituent ply thickness $t=0.05\text{mm}$, strain rate= $9.3 \times 10^{-5}(/s)$). Edge replica observation.

Figure 7. Crack density in CFRP angle-ply laminates with various constituent ply thicknesses as a function of applied strain (strain rate= $9.3 \times 10^{-5}(/s)$).

By using the data obtained by the loading-unloading test, we can evaluate the modulus change. We can estimate also the damage parameter. We can also evaluate the permanent strain. In this study, we consider the effect of fiber angle rotation on the initial Young's modulus. We looked at two kinds of modulus change, one is the apparent one where we used the initial Young's modulus throughout, and the other is the modified one where we used the current Young's modulus considering the fiber rotation. Figure 8 shows crack density and modulus ratio of (+45/-45) angle-ply CFRP laminates with different ply thicknesses as a function of applied strain (the constituent ply thicknesses are (a) 0.6mm, (b) 0.3mm, (c) 0.15mm and (d) 0.05mm). When we look at the data from the laminates with relatively thin constituent plies, the apparent modulus change increases which may be unrealistic. However, when we look at the modified modulus change, it decreases, which implies the significance of the consideration of the effect of fiber rotation. Figure 9 shows the permanent strain in CFRP angle-ply laminates with various constituent ply thicknesses as a function of (a) applied maximum strain and (b) applied maximum stress.

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(a) 0.6mm

(d) 0.05mm

(b) 0.3mm

(c) 0.15mm

Figure 8. Crack density and modulus ratio of (+45/-45) angle-ply CFRP laminates with different ply thicknesses as a function of applied strain. The constituent ply thicknesses are (a) 0.6mm, (b) 0.3mm, (c) 0.15mm and (d) 0.05mm.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. Permanent strain in CFRP angle-ply laminates with various constituent ply thicknesses as a function of (a) applied maximum strain and (b) applied maximum stress.

In this study, an attempt is made to apply the finite strain viscoplasticity model of *unidirectional* composites to *multidirectional* laminated composites. We use Kontou and Spathis' finite strain viscoplasticity model for unidirectional polymeric fiber composites [1]. In the theory, multiplicative decomposition of deformation gradient is used.

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}^e \mathbf{F}^p \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{F}^e and \mathbf{F}^p are elastic and plastic parts of deformation gradient tensor \mathbf{F} .

The velocity gradient tensor \mathbf{L} is defined by the following equation who is divided into its symmetric part \mathbf{D} , rate of deformation tensor, and antisymmetric part \mathbf{W} , the material spin tensor.

$$\mathbf{L} = \dot{\mathbf{F}}\mathbf{F}^{-1} = \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{W} \quad (3)$$

The tensor \mathbf{D} can be additively decomposed into its elastic and plastic parts as

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{D}^e + \mathbf{D}^p \quad (4)$$

and \mathbf{W} can be decomposed as follows

$$\mathbf{W} = \boldsymbol{\omega} + \mathbf{W}^p \quad (5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ is the substructural spin and \mathbf{W}^p is the

material plastic spin.

Kontou and Spathis proposed an elastic-viscoplastic constitutive relation for *unidirectional* polymeric fiber composites as follows.

$$\mathbf{D}^p = \alpha \frac{\dot{\gamma}_1^p}{2} (\mathbf{s} \otimes \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{m} \otimes \mathbf{s}) \quad (6)$$

$$+ \beta \frac{\dot{\gamma}_2^p}{2} (\mathbf{m} \otimes \mathbf{m} - \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n})$$

$$\mathbf{W}^p = \eta \frac{\dot{\gamma}_1^p}{2} (\mathbf{s} \otimes \mathbf{m} - \mathbf{m} \otimes \mathbf{s}) \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{s} , \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{n} denote unit vectors in fiber, in-plane transverse and thickness directions and

$$\dot{\gamma}_1^p = A(\dot{\gamma}) \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{h} \right)^c \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{\gamma}_2^p = A(\dot{\gamma}) \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{h} \right)^c$$

where $A(\dot{\gamma})$ is a function of imposed strain rate $\dot{\gamma}$, h is the hardening modulus and c is a constant.

They employed hypoelasticity constitutive relation,

$$\overset{0}{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{D}^e \quad (9)$$

where $\overset{0}{\sigma}$ is the objective rate of stress and \mathbf{C} is the elasticity tensor which is assumed to be linear.

In this study, the theory is applied to a *multidirectional* laminated composite assuming that the rate of deformation tensor is uniform in the laminate and the stress resultants N_{xy} and N_{yy} is zero. The relation between σ_x and ε_x is obtained. Figure 10 shows the preliminary results. The parameters used are also shown. If we do not consider the effect of fiber angle rotation the stress-strain curve exhibits no hardening behavior, but if we consider the fiber angle rotation, we see the *softening-hardening* behavior which is observed in the experiment. Because the prediction does not consider the effect

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of damages, the prediction goes to high stress level in the high strain regime.

Figure 10. Comparison between the analytical prediction and experimental results of stress-strain relation of angle-ply (45/-45) laminates.

Next, the implementation of the damage model into the finite strain viscoplasticity model is considered. We use Ladeveze and Le Dantec's damage mechanics model [2]. In the model, the thermomechanical potential for damaged ply is assumed to be

$$\rho\Gamma(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, D_s, D_T) = -\frac{1}{2} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{E_1^0} - 2\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} \sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + \\ \frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{(1-D_T)E_1^0} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{(1-D_s)G_{12}^0} \end{array} \right\} \quad (10)$$

The associated forces are

$$Y_s \equiv -\rho \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial D_s} = \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{2(1-D_s)^2 G_{12}^0}, \quad (11)$$

$$Y_T \equiv -\rho \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial D_T} = \frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{2(1-D_T)^2 E_2^0}$$

The damage development is assumed as

$$D_s = \frac{1}{(Y_C^S)^{1/2}} \langle Y^{1/2} - (Y_0)^{1/2} \rangle, \quad (12)$$

$$D_T = \frac{1}{(Y_C^T)^{1/2}} \langle Y^{1/2} - (Y_0)^{1/2} \rangle$$

where $Y = Y_s + bY_T$, $b = \frac{(Y_C^S)^{1/2}}{(Y_C^T)^{1/2}}$

Y_0, Y_C^S, Y_C^T : material constants

Hypoelasticity constitutive relation is modified to include the damage effect which is expressed by

$$\overset{0}{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{C}^d : \mathbf{D}^e \quad (13)$$

$$[\mathbf{C}^d]^{-1} \equiv [\mathbf{S}^d] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1^0} & -\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} & \frac{1}{(1-D_T)E_2^0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-D_s)G_{12}^0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

In Figs.11-14, comparison between the experimental results and the analytical predictions are shown for stress-strain curves, fiber angle as a function of applied strain, apparent modulus change as a function of applied maximum strain and the permanent strain as a function of the applied maximum strain, respectively. A qualitative agreement is obtained.

Figure 11 Stress-strain curves for angle-ply laminates. Comparison between the experimental results and analytical prediction.

Figure 13 Apparent modulus change as the function of applied maximum strain for angle-ply laminates. Comparison between the experimental results and analytical prediction.

Figure 12 Fiber angle as a function of longitudinal applied strain for angle-ply laminates. Comparison between the estimated experimental results and analytical prediction.

Figure 14 Permanent strain as a function of applied maximum strain for angle-ply laminates. Comparison between experimental results and analytical prediction.

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SUMMARY

We evaluated the mechanical behavior and damage behavior in CFRP angle-ply laminates with different constituent ply thickness under tensile loading experimentally. It was found that as the constituent ply thickness decreases, the strength and failure strain increases. We also observed difference in damage behavior. The preliminary results of finite strain viscoplasticity model considering the damage effect for laminated composites are shown. A qualitative agreement is obtained.

References

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